

Realtime Driver Drowsiness Detection Using Machine Learning

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Abstract

Driver drowsiness is one of the leading causes of traffic accidents and has a substantial impact on road safety. Many traffic accidents can be avoided if sleepy drivers were given early warnings. Drowsiness detection systems monitor the driver condition and generate an alarm if drowsiness signs are detected. In this paper, a real-time visual-based driver drowsiness detection system is presented aiming to detect drowsiness by extracting an eye feature called the eye aspect ratio. In the proposed system, which is applied on videos obtained from a public drowsiness detection dataset, the face region is first localized in each frame. Then, the eye region is detected and extracted as the region of interest using facial landmarks detector. Following that, the eye aspect ratio value of each frame is calculated, analyzed, and recorded. Finally, three different classifiers, namely, linear support vector machine, random forest, and sequential neural network, are employed to improve the detection accuracy. Subsequently, the extracted data are classified to determine if the driver's eyes are closed or open. An alarm will then be triggered to alert the drowsy driver if an eye closure is recognized for a specified duration of time.

Keywords—Driver drowsiness detection; eye aspect ratio; support vector machine; random forest; sequential neural network

I. INTRODUCTION

Drowsiness is considered one of the major threats to road safety due to the fact that when a driver enters the microsleep state, the driver's unconsciousness will increase the possibility of causing accidents. Drowsiness can be attributed to the lack of sleeping, tiredness, or mental issues. In 2019, the Ministry of Interior in the UAE reported that an average of two people died per day due to car accidents in the last five years [1]. It was also reported that the main causes for most of these accidents were drowsiness, speeding and changing lanes suddenly, inattentiveness, and crossing red lights. As the concerns regarding this issue are common among multiple countries, many researchers worldwide started searching for a solution. Hence, various techniques were proposed to build a Driver Drowsiness Detection (DDD) system that detects the driver's drowsiness and triggers an alarm when drowsiness is detected. These techniques are categorized into three types according to the features used in the system, namely, vehicular, visual, and non-visual features. In addition, DDD systems use hardware components like sensors and cameras to extract the mentioned features. The collected data are then processed and classified using various ways such as Machine Learning (ML) algorithms which include Support Vector Machine (SVM), convolutional neural network, and hidden Markov model that help to

determine the driver's drowsiness level. The purpose of this study is to develop a visual drowsiness detection system. The system detects the drowsy driver using the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) feature. Moreover, with the help of SVM, Random Forest (RF), and Sequential Neural Network (NN) classifiers, the driver's eye status is classified.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the literature review. Section III illustrates the solution methodology. Section IV presents the results and discussions. Finally, section V concludes the paper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the past decade, many researchers around the world proposed various techniques to address the drowsiness detection problem. One of these techniques depends on visual-based measures. Drowsy people exhibit several visual behaviors that can be detected through changes in their facial features such as the eyes, mouth, and head [2]. Visual measures are the most used features for drowsiness detection due to the fast detection and clear signs of the driver's facial expressions and whether the driver is asleep or awake [3], [4]. Moreover, using these visual measures is considered a popular approach to detect drowsiness due to their non-invasive nature [5]. Many visual features can be detected from the driver's image, such as eye blinking, yawning, and head movement [6]. In a non-invasive way, these features are employed in drowsiness detection through visual observation of the driver's physical condition using cameras and computer vision techniques. Computer vision strategies aim to extract visual characteristics that usually define the driver's degree of drowsiness from video frames [5]. The most used visual features for DDD that depend on computer vision techniques are explained in detail in the following.

Systems that detect driver drowsiness based on yawning focus on analyzing the variation in the driver's mouth geometric shape. This approach considers inspecting the width of the mouth opening, lips position, etc. [7]. However, such systems usually extract additional features from the driver's face in order to obtain more accurate results. For instance, Azim et al. [8] detected drowsiness using pupil movement and yawning. Both parameters were measured based on the information of the eye and mouth. The system worked as follows; first, to ensure the presence of the driver's face within the video frame, the Viola-Jones face detection method is applied. Second, from the face region frame, a mouth window

is extracted. Then, spatial fuzzy c-means clustering is applied to search and locate lips in the window. At the same time, and in another window, the eye section is extracted. From that window, the pupils can be detected based on the inter-pupil distance, angle, and radii. Finally, the collected eyes and mouth data are passed to an SVM classifier that classifies, based on the data's characteristics, the driver state whether drowsy or not. The video data used in the aforementioned work were collected from real-life scenarios at different times of the day.

Other commonly used features in visual-based DDD systems can be extracted from the eyes. Drowsiness detection methods that use eyeblink frequency as a measure compares the regular eye blinking frequency with the eye blinking frequency of a drowsy driver. Naturally, the blinking rate is about ten blinks per minute; however, the blinking rate decreases when the driver is drowsy [9]. In the literature, many studies have been conducted to achieve drowsiness detection based on the eyeblink rate. Rahman et al. [10] introduced a real-time monitoring method based on eye blinking to determine the driver's drowsiness. In that method, first, the Luminosity algorithm is used to convert the colored picture of the eye into grayscale. Second, a Harris corner detector is used to find the two eye corners and one point on the eyelid's lower part. Third, the measurement of the mid-point value between the upper two corner points is calculated. If the distance is near zero, it classifies that the eyes are closed, and thus the driver is drowsy. Fourth, the pixel values of the lid, cornea, and iris of the eye are calculated to detect the eyes' openness, and both of those values will be different for the open eye. Finally, the blinking rate is calculated, and a drowsy situation will be reported if the rate is reduced. Their system obtained an accuracy of 94%.

Compared to that work, Soukupova and Cech [11] suggested a simple yet efficient real-time algorithm to detect eye blinking using facial landmark detectors. The work introduced a scalar quantity that relies on the ratio of the height of the eye to its width called EAR. The EAR is used to measure the eye openness degree in each frame, and a blink is detected at the location where a sharp drop occurs in the EAR value. In their experiment, an SVM classifier was used to detect eye blinks as a pattern of EAR values in a short temporal window. The system showed an accuracy of up to 90% and varied according to the facial landmark detectors and the datasets used.

Head movement-based detection is another common feature in visual-based DDD systems whereby the different head movements can be used to indicate a drowsy state. For example, when a driver is drowsy, the driver's head starts to sway. Another trait is mentioned in [2] which indicates that the head-nodding frequency increases as the drivers nod their heads more frequently trying to avoid sleeping. Moreover, according to [12], when taking the forehead as a reference, the head which poses in different angles can be considered another trait. Authors in [13] used an infrared sensor to track head movement and detect the driver's drowsiness. Another commonly used sensor is the Micro-Nod Detection System. The sensor detects the micro-sleep by analyzing the head position in real-time. The change in the driver's head position is tracked on x , y , and z coordinates. After attaining this feature,

it is then handled by ML algorithms such as convolutional neural network, SVM, and hidden Markov model [14]. The authors in [15] used a 3D deep Neural Network with Kernelized Correlation and Kalman filters. The experimental results showed an accuracy of 88%.

To contribute to the current works of drowsiness detection systems, this study aims to build a driver drowsiness detection system that detects drowsiness based on the visual measures, specifically, the EAR feature while achieving low complexity, high performance, and adapting to the current situation of the COVID-19 pandemic where drivers wear masks.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed DDD system is illustrated in this section by providing the system design, description of the used dataset, and the three main steps of the implementation process, which are: (1) pre-processing; (2) feature extraction; and (3) model selection.

A. System Design

The proposed driver drowsiness detection system is illustrated in Fig. 1. The DDD system is composed of five main steps. A video of the driver's face is captured in step one, and its frames are extracted. Step two is pre-processing. In this step, first, each frame is converted from BGR image to Grayscale image. Then, face detection is applied to detect the driver's face within the frame using the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) face detector from the Dlib library. Lastly in the pre-processing step, the shape_predictor_68_face_landmarks Dlib module is used to get the facial landmarks and extract the eye region. In step three, the EAR is calculated for each frame and stored in a list. In step four, when the first 15 EAR values have been stored in the list, the system starts inputting the 15-element vector to the trained model. Then the input data will be classified as closed-eye or open-eye. In the last step, if closed eyes were detected for more than 15 consecutive times, which is equivalent to 1 second, the driver will be classified as drowsy, and an alarm will sound. The following subsection illustrates the used dataset.

B. Dataset

To implement this system, a video dataset provided by the National Tsing Hua University Computer Vision Lab's DDD (NTHU DDD) is used [16]. This dataset consists of 36 subjects of different facial characteristics, ethnicities, and genders recorded under different scenarios (e.g., no glasses, wearing glasses, wearing sunglasses, at night without glasses, and at night with glasses) during the day and night. In this paper, parts from this dataset were used, including five subjects for the training dataset, and three subjects for the testing dataset driving with and without glasses both during daytime.

C. Preprocessing

To pre-process and prepare the extracted frames for the next step, each frame is converted from BGR colored image to a grayscale image. The color conversion is done by applying the `cv2.cvtColor()` method from the OpenCV library. The

Fig. 1. Proposed driver drowsiness detection system

driver's face is then extracted from each frame using Dlib's

HOG face detector where the `dlib.get_frontal_face_detector()` method is utilized. This method detects the faces in the images and returns the coordinates of a rectangle frame surrounding

the face region. After that, the Dlib facial landmarks detector is used to detect the key facial structures, including the eye region.

D. Feature Extraction

Different features have been proposed to model the driver drowsiness detection system. In this paper, the modeling is based on the EAR metric. According to [17], the EAR feature assembles several quality characteristics. The traditional image processing method for detecting eye blinking includes steps like eye localization, determining the whites of the eyes through thresholding, and indicating eye blinking by tracking the disappearance of the white region of the eye during a time period. In contrast, the EAR does not require any image processing technicalities. Instead, it is a more straightforward solution that depends on the computation of the ratio of the distance between previously determined facial landmarks of the driver's eyes. In general, this metric observes the eye landmarks based on computing the ratio of six coordinates as illustrated in Fig. 2 [18]. Coordinates are numbered beginning

from the left corner of the eye and revolving clockwise. The authors in [11] explained that the difference between coordinates p_2 and p_6 , p_3 and p_5 , diminishes when the eyes are completely closed. As such, the EAR value drops down to zero, as shown in Fig. 2. On the other hand, the EAR value remains approximately constant when the eye is open.

Fig. 2. EAR change over time [18]

The equation used to calculate the EAR value is given in (1). As explained in [17], the functional characterization of the EAR equation is that all the six coordinates from p_1 to p_6 are 2-dimensional. Also, as shown in (1), the nominator computes the distance between the vertical points. On the other hand, the denominator computes the distance between the horizontal points. The authors in [11] pointed out that the denominator is multiplied by two to balance the weight of the two sets in the nominator. Thus, the next implementation step is to calculate the EAR of the driver's eyes in each frame and store these values in a list. This is achieved by writing a function to calculate the EAR in Python, then passing each eye's coordinates to that function as a parameter. The returned EAR value is then stored in a list for later use.

$$EAR = \frac{\|p_2 - p_6\| + \|p_3 - p_5\|}{2\|p_1 - p_4\|} \quad (1)$$

According to [11], the eye blink is a quick closing and reopening of the eye. Each person has a slightly different blinking pattern. It mainly differs in the closing and opening speed, blink duration, and the degree to which the eye is closed. Normal eye blink lasts approximately 100 to 400 msec. As mentioned before, a very low EAR value means that the eye is closing in that image. In order to detect the different blinks for each person, and since one EAR value per frame will not help to recognize the eye blinks correctly, this method trains a classifier that uses a large temporal window of frames as an input. For every 30 f/s videos, the EAR of the N th frame is computed, along with the EAR for $N-7$ and $N+7$ frames. Then, by concatenating these EARs, a 15-dimensional feature vector is formed for each frame. The reason for taking the 7 neighboring frames for each N th frame is to capture the actual state of the eye at that frame, either open or closed. An EAR threshold of 0.2 was set to reflect the openness of the eye. Next, to label the input data, the following procedure is applied: if more than 7 elements of that 15-dimensional vector

are greater than the threshold, that vector would be labeled as an open eye with the label 0. Otherwise, a label 1 will be given to the vector indicating that the eye is closed as shown in Fig. 3. The latter step is implemented using a scanning window that moves continuously through the EAR list, as shown in Fig. 4. Thus, a 15-frame vector is taken in each iteration, labeled as 0 (open eyes) or 1 (closed eyes), and stored in another list.

0.19	0.22	0.2	0.23	0.25	0.26	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.2	0.18	0.24	0.19	0.16	1
0.22	0.2	0.23	0.25	0.26	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.2	0.18	0.24	0.19	0.16	0.26	0
0.2	0.23	0.25	0.26	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.2	0.18	0.24	0.19	0.16	0.26	0.18	0
0.23	0.25	0.26	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.2	0.18	0.24	0.19	0.16	0.26	0.18	0.2	1

Fig.3. Labeling the EAR vectors

Fig.4. Scanning window through the driver's EAR list

E. Model Selection

Herein, the procedure followed to train the SVM, RF, and Sequential NN models for detecting driver drowsiness is illustrated. After extracting the EAR values, two main data pre-processing steps are implemented: data splitting and data balancing. Using the `train_test_split()` function from the Scikit learn library, the data is split into a 70:30 ratio, 70% training, and 30% testing. As for data balancing, in the training set, the majority class had 62802 instances labeled as 0, and the minority class had only 9523 labeled as 1. To solve the issue of imbalanced data, the oversampling technique was applied to increase the closed eye class that is labeled as 1. Specifically, Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) is used to balance the data. SMOTE is an oversampling technique that balances data by creating new minority class instances that are obtained by interpolating between several minority class samples that lie together. After balancing the dataset, ML and deep learning models are applied for classification purposes. The model uses a 15-dimension input (15 consecutive EARs) and returns one category (e.g., open: 0 or closed: 1). In this work, three models were used: SVM, RF, and sequential NN model. All the parameters of these models have been tuned and optimized using grid search hyperparameters.

SVM is a supervised ML model that linearly classifies two groups of data [19]. The SVM classifier is a typical classifier that was utilized in numerous other DDD research work [20]. The design of the SVM model aims to find a hyperplane for N number of features. In this system, the Support Vector Classification was imported from the Scikit learn library.

RF is a well-known and efficient ML algorithm that is dependent on model aggregation ideas. This classifier is generally utilized for binary classification which helps to achieve the desired classification in the utilized data. It is worth mentioning that RF was first introduced by Leo Breiman [21]. The RF classifier used in this work also belongs to the Scikit learn library.

Sequential NN is the easiest way to build a model in Keras [22]. The Sequential NN classifier is selected to apply a deep learning classifier and observe if it will give better outcomes. This model allows building a model layer by layer. Each layer has weights that correspond to the following layer [23]. In the Sequential model, the Sequential class is created, and model layers are created and added [24]. In this Sequential model, a neural network that has six layers is created as follows: one input layer, four hidden layers, and one output layer. A vector of 15 EAR values is inputted to the input layer. In the four hidden layers, 16 nodes were added, each using Rectified Linear Units as the activation function (ReLU). ReLU is a half-rectified function; if it receives a negative input, it returns 0, and if it receives a positive value, that same value is returned [25]. Thus, it allows for the deep learning model to account for non-linearities and specific interaction effects. The output layer has one output node which uses the sigmoid activation function to squeeze all the values between 0 and 1 into a sigmoid curve. The output layer classifies the output into either 1 for closed eyes or 0 for opened eyes.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To test the proposed system, videos from the NTHU DDD testing dataset were used. The frames were extracted, pre-processed, and the EAR feature was extracted as explained earlier. Then, the collected data were fed to each of the three trained models. The confusion matrix, accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were used to evaluate the testing and training results.

Table I lists the results of the DDD system. Referring to Table I, the results indicate that the RF model achieved the best performance compared to the linear SVM and Sequential NN models. Looking at the training results, it can be seen that the RF model scored 100% at every metric. Simultaneously, in the testing results, the RF model achieved an accuracy of 99% with a 96% and 99% sensitivity and specificity, respectively. As for the sequential NN model, it showed the second-best performance after the RF model. This model has shown 97% at all metrics. As for the testing results, 97% accuracy, 96% sensitivity, and 97% specificity were acquired. In terms of the linear SVM, it showed the lowest results compared to the other two models. The linear SVM model achieved an accuracy of 96% in the training results, while in testing it achieved only 95%. Concerning sensitivity and specificity, this model gave 97% and 95% respectively in both training and testing. Regardless of wearing eyeglasses or not, our models performed well in both scenarios.

To visualize the performance of these models, the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and the Precision-Recall

TABLE I.

RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED DDD SYSTEM USING TRAINING AND TESTING DATA

Training			
Metric \ Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Linear SVM	0.96	0.97	0.95
RF	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sequential NN	0.97	0.97	0.97
Testing			
Metric \ Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Linear SVM	0.95	0.97	0.95
RF	0.99	0.96	0.99
Sequential NN	0.97	0.96	0.97

curves were plotted. The ROC curve describes the performance of binary classification models in terms of how well the model predicts the positive class when the actual outcome prediction is positive [26]. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) score represents the degree of separability and reflects the total area under the ROC curve. A model that has a high AUC is better at predicting true positive and true negative actual outcomes. Fig. 5 illustrates the ROC curve for the balanced training data. Much like the ROC curve, the Precision-Recall curve is a good tool to evaluate binary classification algorithms [26]. Also, in this type of plots, a high AUC model reflects better predicting performance. Fig. 6 illustrates the precision-recall curve of the imbalanced testing data.

It is observed from Fig. 5 that all three models have high AUC values in the training results. However, the RF model reflects the best performance here as well, with an AUC of 1.00. Similarly, when analyzing Fig. 6 which represents the testing results, we can see that the RF model shows the best performance with an AUC value of 0.992 compared to the sequential NN model with an AUC value of 0.981 and the SVM model with an AUC value of 0.971.

From the aforementioned, it can be realized that the overall results demonstrated high accuracy in detecting eye openness. That led to developing a system that is capable of identifying long eye closures from blinking. The experiments and tests in this work agree with previous research work of [11] and [27] that used the EAR feature to indicate drowsiness. In addition, these results have shown higher accuracy than Soukupova and Cech [11] that achieved around 90% accuracy. Furthermore, it succeeded in detecting the driver's face while wearing a mask. When comparing these results with other DDD methods that used the NTHU DDD dataset, as demonstrated in Table II, it has been found that the proposed method using the RF model had the highest accuracy. It should be noted that the proposed DDD system has some limitations. Since only the EAR is used as a drowsiness indicator, false alarms might rise when the driver is laughing or yawning. Moreover, the performance of the HOG detector can deteriorate in some scenarios. This includes having more subjects in the video frame and intensity changes during the drive.

Fig. 5. ROC curve for the training data

Fig. 6. The Precision-Recall curve for the testing data

TABLE II. COMPARISON WITH OTHER METHODS THAT USED THE NTHU DDD DATASET

Method	Accuracy
This work	99%
Gamma fatigue detection network [28]	97.06%
3D convolutional networks [29]	92.19%
Simple averaging approach [30]	85%
Condition-adaptive representation learning framework [31]	76.2%

In future work, a mobile application can be developed to implement this DDD system to allow easy use for users while driving. Moreover, to overcome the limitations, different adaptations and improvements can be done such as widening the region of interest of this system by including the mouth and head movements. Thus, the system will achieve more accurate results when it comes to classifying drowsiness from alertness. In addition, a specially equipped camera can be added to adapt to the intensity changes and sustain the main object detection. The task of such a camera is to focus on detecting only the driver's face in all positions. Furthermore, some additional hardware can be incorporated to help expand the system's usefulness. This component could be an external strobe light to alert the other road users and drivers. Also, a buzzer can be attached to the driver's seat, and whenever drowsiness occurs, the buzzer will be activated causing the seat to vibrate thus alerting the drowsy driver.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a real-time visual-based drowsiness detection system. The proposed system used live camera images to implement real-time drowsiness detection. To overcome the challenge of false detection of closed eyes, ML classifiers were applied in the final stage. If drowsiness is detected, an alarm will be initiated to alert the driver. Following the training stage, the three ML models were retested, and the results showed that the RF model achieved the best performance with 99% accuracy. While car accidents caused by drowsy drivers pose one of the main threats to road safety, drowsy detection systems are continuously improving over time. Many communities worldwide believe that such an engineering solution could prevent the loss of lives and resources. Thus, we hope that this DDD system will contribute to this field.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Sebugwaawo. (2019, Mar. 13). *2 People killed daily in crashes on UAE roads during last five years* [Online]. Available: <https://www.khaleejtimes.com/news/transport/2-people-killed-daily-in-crashes-on-uae-roads-during-last-five-years>.
- [2] G. Sikander and S. Anwar, "Driver Fatigue Detection Systems: A Review," In *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 2339-2352, June 2019.
- [3] B. G. Pratama, I. Ardiyanto and T. B. Adji, "A Review on Driver Drowsiness Based on Image, Bio-Signal, and Driver Behavior," In *2017 3rd International Conference on Science and Technology - Computer (ICST)*, Yogyakarta, 2017, pp. 70-75, doi:10.1109/ICSTC.2017.8011855.
- [4] S. Kaplan, M. A. Guvensan, A. G. Yavuz, and Y. Karalurt, "Driver Behavior Analysis for Safe Driving: A Survey," In *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2015, pp. 3017-3032.
- [5] Q. Ji and X. Yang, "Real-Time Eye, Gaze, and Face Pose Tracking for Monitoring Driver Vigilance," *Real-Time Imaging*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 357-377, 2002.
- [6] A. Mittal, K. Kumar, S. Dhamija, and M. Kaur, "Head movement-based driver drowsiness detection: A review of state-of-art techniques," In *2016 IEEE International Conference on Engineering and Technology (ICETECH)*, Coimbatore, India, 2016, pp. 903-908.
- [7] M. Ramzan, H. U. Khan, S. M. Awan, A. Ismail, M. Ilyas and A. Mahmood, "A Survey on State-of-the-Art Drowsiness Detection Techniques," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 61904-61919, 2019.
- [8] T. Azim, M. A. Jaffar and A. M. Mirza, "Automatic Fatigue Detection of Drivers through Pupil Detection and Yawning Analysis," *2009 Fourth International Conference on Innovative Computing, Information and Control (ICICIC)*, Kaohsiung, 2009, pp. 441-445, doi:10.1109/ICICIC.2009.119.
- [9] M. Saradadevi and P. Bajaj, "Driver fatigue detection using mouth and yawning analysis," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Netw. Secur.*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 183-188, Jun. 2008.
- [10] A. Rahman, M. Sirshar, and A. Khan, "Real time drowsiness detection using eye blink monitoring," in *Proc. Nat. Softw. Eng. Conf. (NSEC)*, Dec. 2015, pp. 1-7.
- [11] T. Soukupova and J. Cech, "Real-time eye blink detection using facial landmarks," in *21st Computer Vision Winter Workshop*. Slovenia, 2016, pp. 1-8.
- [12] S. Arun, S. Kenneth and M. Murugappan, "Detecting Driver Drowsiness Based on Sensors: A Review," *MDPI. Sensors*, vol. 12, pp. 16937-16953. doi:10.3390/s121216937
- [13] R. C. Coetzer and G. P. Hancke, "Driver fatigue detection: A survey," *AFRICON 2009*, Nairobi, 2009, pp. 1-6, doi:10.1109/AFRICON.2009.5308101.
- [14] M. Ngxande, J. Tapamo, and M. Burke, "Driver drowsiness detection using Behavioral measures and machine learning techniques: A Review of state-of-art techniques," In *2017 Pattern Recognition Association of South Africa and Robotics and Mechatronics (PRASA-RobMech)*, Bloemfontein, South Africa, 2017, pp. 156-161.
- [15] K. Dwivedi, K. Biswaranjan, and A. Sethi, "Drowsy driver detection using representation learning," *Souvenir 2014 IEEE Int. Adv. Comput. Conf. IACC 2014*, pp. 995-999, 2014.
- [16] C. H. Weng, Y. H. Lai and S. H. Lai, "Driver Drowsiness Detection via Hierarchical Temporal Deep Belief Network," In *Asian Conference on Computer Vision Workshop on Driver Drowsiness Detection from Video*, Taipei, Taiwan, Nov. 2016. ROSEBROCK, A. 2017. Eyeblink detection with OpenCV, Python, and dlib. Pyimagesearch. https://www.pyimagesearch.com/2017/04/24/eye-blink-detection-opencv-python-dlib/_mju4CFQAAAAAdAAAAABAK.
- [17] A. Rosebrock. (2017, Apr. 24). *Eyeblink detection with OpenCV, Python, and dlib* [Online]. Available: https://www.pyimagesearch.com/2017/04/24/eye-blink-detection-opencv-python-dlib/_mju4CFQAAAAAdAAAAABAK.
- [18] Datahacker. (2020, Oct 6). *How to detect eye blinking in videos using dlib and OpenCV in Python* [online]. Available: <https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=http%3A%2F%2Fdatahacker.rs%2F011-how-to-detect-eye-blinking-in-videos-using-dlib-and-opencv-in-python%2F&psig=AOvVaw3DV2hMmbV15Xlrln1hy3i&ust=1612461126891000&source=images&cd=vfe&ved=0CAMQjB1qFwoTCIDz8>.
- [19] R. Gandhi, "Support Vector Machine - Introduction to Machine Learning Algorithms," *Medium*, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://towardsdatascience.com/support-vector-machine-introduction-to-machine-learning-algorithms-934a444fca47>.
- [20] A. Bamidele, K. Kamardin, N. Abd Aziz, S. Sam, I. Ahmed, A. Azizan, N. Bani, and H. Kaidi, "Non-intrusive Driver Drowsiness Detection based on Face and Eye Tracking," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 549-569, 2019.
- [21] L. Breiman, "Random Forests," in *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5-32, 2001, doi:10.1023/A:1010933404324.
- [22] Keras, *Keras* [Online]. Available: <https://keras.io/api/models/sequential/>
- [23] E. Allibhai. (2018, Sep. 17). "Building A Deep Learning Model using Keras," *Towardsdatascience* [Online]. Available: <https://towardsdatascience.com/building-a-deep-learning-model-using-keras-1548ca149d37>.
- [24] S. Paul. (2018, Aug. 9). "Keras Sequential Api," *Medium* [Online]. Available: <https://medium.com/@subhamoy.paul986/keras-sequential-api-72e45c39259b>.
- [25] DeepAI. "What is a Rectified Linear Unit?," *DeepAI* [Online]. Available: <https://deeptai.org/machine-learning-glossary-and-terms/rectified-linear-units>.
- [26] J. Brownlee. (2018, Aug. 31). *How to Use ROC Curves and Precision-Recall Curves for Classification in Python* [Online]. Available: <https://machinelearningmastery.com/roc-curves-and-precision-recall-curves-for-classification-in-python/>.
- [27] C. B. S. Maior, M. J. Moura, J. M. M. Santana and I. D. Lins, "Real-time classification for autonomous drowsiness detection using eye aspect ratio," in *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 158, pp. 113505, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113505>.
- [28] W. Liu, J. Qian, Z. Yao, X. Jiao, and J. Pan, "Convolutional two-stream network using multi-facial feature fusion for driver fatigue detection," *Future Internet*, vol. 11, p. 115, 2019.
- [29] Y. Ed-Doughmi, N. Idrissi, and Y. Hbali, "Real-time system for driver fatigue detection based on a recurrent neuronal network," *Journal of Imaging*, vol. 6, p. 8, 2020.
- [30] M. Dua, R. Singla, S. Raj, and A. Jangra, "Deep CNN models-based ensemble approach to driver drowsiness detection," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 33, pp. 3155-3168, 2021.
- [31] J. Yu, S. Park, S. Lee, and M. Jeon, "Driver drowsiness detection using condition-adaptive representation learning framework," *IEEE transactions on intelligent transportation systems*, vol. 20, pp. 4206-4218, 2018.